

CONDUCTING A NEEDS ANALYSIS FOR ESP STUDENTS TO IMPROVE EFFECTIVENESS

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The group of target learners consists of 18-22 year-old freshman students studying at the faculty of Tourism and Hospitality at Management Development Institute of Singapore (MDIS) in Tashkent. The group encompasses 20 students: 12 boys and 8 girls and also varies in scope of nationality, including Uzbek, Russian, Tajik, Kazak, Afghan, Arab and Indian. Minimum 5.5 IELTS overall band score is required to apply for the University, and the students' current level is already B1 minimum and some of them are of B2.

Coming from the description of CEFR companion (2020), the learners' receptive skills have developed enough to comprehend straightforward and factual data with general or specific details on topics common in everyday life and job-related situations or of their field of interests if delivered in a clear, generally familiar variety. As for their productive skills, they "can reasonably fluently sustain a straightforward description of one of a variety of subjects within their field of interest, presenting it as a linear sequence of points" and produce simple, connected, in a linear sequence and their field of interest relevant texts (CEFR, 2020, p. 62).

Objectives. As a branch of ESP, the EAP class aims to teach students the content in match with required language. Having EAP class in synchronic with content aims to enable students' development on academic reading, writing, and critical thinking skills through the analysis of academic texts related to the field tourism and hospitality. To ensure students make interpretations of ideas, judgments or claims of others in the very content critically and properly, it is wise to get students prepared to utilise higher order thinking skills, as Smith (2012) mentioned that "if we are ever going to create college-level writers, we must begin by creating college-level readers" (p.61).

Interaction and Instruction. The most effective way to accomplish the needs of the students is through a communicative approach of teaching. CLT is the most appropriate method which can be applied for this group of learners, because the need to improve their speaking skills and their job requires good command of communication and cooperation. "Communicative language teaching (CLT) has become a term for methods and curricula that embrace both the goals and the processes of classroom learning, for teaching practice that views competence in terms of social interaction" (Savignon, 1991, p. 263). Task-based instruction is also efficient because it enables students to practise their problem solving skills using English in an authentic way. It is helpful for learners as they can come across those situations in their future careers. According to Dudley-Evans and St. John (1998), state that "needs analysis is an important component of ESP teaching, as it ensures that learners are learning language that is directly applicable to their chosen field" (p. 224). This approach can help learners to develop the language skills that they need for their specific career goals. In addition to CLT and task-based instruction, there are other effective methods and approaches that can be utilised for English for Specific Purposes (ESP) learners. One such method is the use of authentic materials, which are relevant to the learners' future career goals. Hutchinson and Waters (1987), "the use of authentic materials (e.g. texts, videos, audio recordings, etc.) can expose students to the real language and situations they are likely to encounter in their specific field"

(p. 80). This can help learners to develop their language skills in a contextually appropriate way. Also, the implication of technology-enhanced language learning can also be effective for ESP learners. As suggested by Warschauer and Healey (1998), "the use of computer-assisted language learning (CALL) and other technological tools can enhance language learning by providing opportunities for learners to engage in interactive and communicative activities" (p. 4). This approach can help learners to develop their language skills in a more engaging and interactive way.

Resources. Based on the content, academic articles and research papers related to tourism and hospitality can be used effectively. These would provide students with the opportunity to practice reading and analyzing academic texts in their field of interest. Access to these materials and resources can be obtained by utilizing the internet, digital libraries, and academic databases. Since the learners are attending a university, they will have access to library resources and online academic databases through their university's library. In addition, materials can be sourced the internet or created specifically for the course. According to Savova (2018), "In the EAL classroom, along with teachers and students, materials are one of three main instructional components" (p. 2). Teachers can also develop quizzes and discussions to assess learners' reading comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and writing skills. Role plays, simulations are also applicable as they can be used in an authentic context which is beneficial for learners.

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